

The Effect of Parents Teachers Associations (PTA) Cooperation on Pupils Academic Achievement: A Case of Public Primary Schools in Eldoret West Sub-County, Uasin Gishu County

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Abstract:

The main aim of this paper was to determine the extent of the effect of Parents Teacher Association (PTA) cooperation on pupils academic achievement in public primary schools in Eldoret West Sub-County, Uasin Gishu County. The study targeted class eight learners, class teachers and PTA representatives in 153 public primary schools. The sample of the study comprised 46 schools, 46 members of PTA, 46 class teachers and 249 class eight learners. Piloting was conducted to enable ascertain validity and reliability of the instrument. The Content and face validity of the of the instrument was considered by engaging the expertise of the lecturers at the department. Reliability of the instruments was established by capturing data on SPSS data sheet and conduction reliability analysis. A Cronbach's coefficient for the teachers' and learners questionnaire attained was 0.68 and 0.71 respectively. The study used questionnaire and interview schedule to collect primary data, while secondary data was collected from pupils' KCPE performance records. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics such as means, percentages and standard deviations, and inferential statistics such as simple linear regression. Data was presented in the form of frequency tables and charts. The study findings indicated that the cooperation of parents significantly affected the overall performance of the school, and 14.1% of the cooperation contributes to performance. The paper recommends that MOE strengthens PTA as an important organ charged with many roles in the schools

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Parents Teachers Association (PTA), Academic Achievement

Introduction

The importance of parental involvement in the education of their children is not a new concept to public schools. In fact, research has shown that parents play a key role in their academic achievement of their children (Blazer, 2005 and Tinkler, 2002). In addition, there is considerable evidence that parental involvement leads to a plethora of benefits for the student, their families, as well as the total school. These benefits occur regardless of the language that they speak, the socioeconomic status, racial, or ethnic/racial background or the parents' educational level (Boethel, 2003; Cassity et al., 2000; and Henderson & Mapp, 2002). Schools must create meaningful parental involvement activities that engage parents in educational decision-making, in leadership roles, and in school governance. In most cases parents are involved in attending a regularly scheduled parent-teacher conference, attending a school or class event, volunteered or served on a school committee, school fundraising, and meeting with a guidance counselor (NHES, 2013). Mutodi (2014) affirms that parental involvement affects student performance. Similarly, Oludipe (2009) indicated that there is a positive relationship between parental involvement in early literacy acquisition and students' science achievement. A related study by Olatoye, Agbatogun, and Olajumoke (2009) indicated that parental involvement accounts for 16.1% of the total variance in mathematics achievement of primary school pupils and 13.5% of the total variance in pupils' achievement in science. This showed that parental involvement is an important predictor of mathematics and science achievement. The government of Kenya has done its part to ensure parents participate in governance and decision making on education matters of their children.

However, Despite this, parental involvement seems to be varied depending on the family characteristics. Variation in levels of parental involvement in tin children's learning at home and at school is strongly influenced by family socioeconomic status (SES) (Boethel, 2003). On the other hand, Desimone (1999) indicates that ethnic and cultural backgrounds between parents and teachers also influence parents' participation in the education of their children (Desimone, 1999). It is a concern that parents in Eldoret West Sub-County, find it difficult to be involved in parental activities directed to school or education issues of

their children (UG CIDP, 2013). The parents are engulfed in a busy working environment with hectic schedules, thereby running out of time to spend with their children. In effect, involvement in the education of their children has suffered. The parental characteristics of the study area have it that majority; particularly those who hail from the vast rural parts of the sub-county have low socio-economic status (KNBS Census, 2009). This scenario echoes Lee & Bowen (2006) that parents with low SES and from different ethnic and cultural background than the mainstream culture, whose children would most benefit from parental involvement are more likely to find it difficult to become and remain involved (Lee & Bowen, 2006). In addition, Studies conducted in an African setting, such as the case of Ghana, (Nyarko & Vorgelegt, 2007; Topor, Keane, Shelton, & Calkins, 2010), suggests that parental or guardian involvement is associated positively with students' performance in school. Taylor et al. (2006) hint that a greater appreciation of the beliefs that underlie parents' decisions about becoming involved in their children's education is needed (Taylor et al., 2004). The way in which parents feel about schools and the emotional connections that they have in school may influence the kinds of attitudes towards school, and their children assume. It is for this reason that the current study would like to investigate parental involvement and achievement of the pupils. Thus this paper sought to answer the following questions.

- (i) *What was the extent of parental involvement in helping and supervising their children's academic work at home?*
- (ii) *What was the effect of Parents and teachers' associations (PTA) cooperation on pupils academic achievement?*

Theoretical framework

This study was guided by Social and Cultural Capital by Bourdieu (1977). Socio-cultural Capital theory postulates that parents' involvement in the educational life of their children is based on the social and cultural capital they are endowed with. Social capital can be produced through various kinds of social relations (Gardner, 2005). Parent-child interaction and communication are home-based social capital. Parental involvement in school, such as in parent-teacher associations (PTA), facilitates parents' relationships with teachers and other adults in the school. Pong et al. (2005) reported these types of social relationships in the family and in the school increase the social capital available to a child. The use of the theory is justified by the fact that the theories recognize the role played by the parents, school and the community in the education of all children in the family and the wider community. The educational development of the children is contributed by the school, which is comprised of the teachers and the school management. On the other hand, the community is comprised of the family, other parents of other children within the same community. In addition, the network endowed with a particular child through their parents may come from multiple sources called relations.

Material and methods.

This study employed the descriptive survey research design. The research population comprised class eight learners, teachers and PTA members in public primary schools in Eldoret West Sub County. Each standard 8 learners had equal and independent chances of being selected to participate in the study. The sample was drawn from 153 public primary schools in Eldoret West Sub County. The study used multistage sampling to select a 30% of schools from each strata to be included in the study. Random sampling was used to obtain the actual schools that formed part of the study.

The sample of the learners were 249. The researcher used questionnaires, interview schedules and documents analysis. The reliability test was using reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) obtained. A Cronbach's coefficient for the teachers' and learners questionnaire were 0.681 and 0.709 respectively. Nunally (in Panayides, 2013) indicates that coefficient of at least 0.7 indicated a good measure of reliability measure (Panayides, 2013). Modeling using simple regression was done to quantify the effect of each aspect of parental involvement (independent variable) and academic achievement (dependent variable). Data from open-ended questionnaires items were grouped under broad themes and converted into frequency counts, and descriptive statistics included means percentage and standard deviation.

Results

The Extent of Parental involvement in education

The study sought to explore the extent to which parents are getting involved in the education of their children. The pupils were asked if their parents involved themselves in school activities such as parent orientation and socialization activities, formal parent-teacher meetings about child's progress and parents information sessions. The study findings indicated that majority of the parents involve themselves in school activities since the pupils who indicated that their parents involved themselves in school activities were 199(79.9%) as opposed to 32(12.2%) who did not involve themselves in school activities. Five percent 12(5.0%) indicated that their parents get involved somehow in the school activities.

Table 1 pupils views on parents involvement in school activities

Response	Frequency	Percent
Yes	199	79.9
No	32	12.7
Somehow	12	5.0
Not sure	6	2.3
Total	249	100.0

Source; Research findings, 2017

Some studies such as those conducted by The National Center for Education Statistics (NCES) in the united states have gone ahead and indicated school or school-related activities that parents usually participate. The most common school-related activity that parents were reported participating in during the school year was attending a general school or a parent-teacher organization or association (PTO/PTA) meeting at 87% (NCES, 2012). In addition, 76% of parents were reported to be attending a regularly scheduled parent-teacher conference; 74% had parents who attended a school or class event while 42% had parents who volunteered or served on a school committee.

Further, 58% had parents who participated in school fundraising; and 33 percent had parents who met with a guidance counselor (NCES, 2012). The results of Table 4.4 is consistent with the results of Table 4.5, where the pupils were asked the extent to which their parent got involved in school activities. The research findings indicated that participation of the majority 204(81.9%) of the parents was good or excellent. Out of this participation of 147(59.1%) was excellent while a 57(22.8%) was good.

Figure 1 Pupils opinion on parent's participation in school activities

The opinion of the teachers was also sought on the extent of the parental involvement, and the results were consistent with those of the learners. However, the proportion of the parents who were involved mattered a lot. There is a concern, however on the proportions of the parents who were not involved 12(4.6%) or fairly involved 90(36.3%) in the education of their children (Table 4.5). Broethel (2003), indicates that there are variations in levels of parental involvement in children's learning at home depending on many factors. One of this factor is socio-economic status (SES) of the family (Boethel, 2003).

There are as many factors as well but are subject to vary because of differences in educational level (Arias, 2008), ethnic and cultural backgrounds (Desimone, 1999). Parental involvement may also vary because of differences in ethnic and cultural backgrounds between parents and teachers (Desimone, 1999).

Table 2 Teacher’s view on parent’s participating in school activities

Involvement	Frequency	Percent
Not involved	12	4.6
Fairly involved	90	36.3
Very involved	147	59.1
Total	249	100.0

Source; Research findings, 2017

Effect of Parents teachers’ associations (PTA) cooperation on pupils academic achievement

The scores for the PTA of each school were arrived at by posing some questions to the PTA representatives. The responses were scored on a five-point Likert scale and the means obtained for each school PTA. A mean of 3.76 ± 0.565 points was obtained with the lowest school having a score of 2 and a maximum of 5. The cooperation of the PTA for each school was determined together with its overall performance index (or mean grade).

The Academic achievement (AC) comprised the dependent variable while the PTA cooperation comprised of (PTAC) comprised the independent variable. PTA cooperation was measured on a five-point scale with the highest cooperation tending toward five (5) and the lowest cooperation tending towards one (1). The cooperation was determined for each school together with the overall performance index of the school. Modeling was done using simple linear regression in a bid to predict academic performance based on PTA level of cooperation. The equation took the form:

$$AC = \beta_0 + \beta_1 (PTAC) \dots\dots\dots i$$

Where PTAC is the Independent variable
AC is the Academic Achievement

Therefore the equation(s) with regard to the variables are as follows:

For PTA cooperation and Performance;

$$AC = 3.988 + 0.523 x * PTAC$$

Table 3 Coefficient of Regression model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	3.988	0.740		5.386	.003
PTAC	0.523	195	0.376	2.688	0.10

Source; Research findings, 2017

From the equation, the coefficient in which the PTAC is its factor is very small, and this is consistent with the fact that little contribution (no significance) (14.1%) of the PTAC on the AC (Table 4).

Table 4 Regression model

Statistics				
R				
Year = 2008 (Selected)	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
	.396	.141	.122	0.728

Based on this results, the study argues on this basis that, PTA contributes to the academic performance of the school. Therefore, PTA cooperation in all aspects of the school is important to the performance of the school. Most schools that parents and teachers work together and make deliberations on the school and adhere to the policies, they perform well. This is because when parents show interest and love the school and participate, the children will also love the school and want to be associated with it. Teachers will also feel that they are supported by parents, and their attitude towards the school and the children would be positive.

Supportive parents will always strive to better the school by improving facilities, thereby improving the learning environment and this will improve the performance of the learners.

Research by Barrera et al. indicates that parents play a key role in the academic achievement of their children (Barrera, 2002; Blazer, 2005; Cassity & Harris, 2000; Cotton & Winkelund, 2001; Epstein, 1987; 1991; and Tinkler, 2002). PTA is a body established to promote quality care, nutritional and health status of the pupils and maintain the good working relationship between teachers and parents (Basic Education bill, 2014). PTA membership is a representative body and virtually represents the parents in the school. Good leadership of PTA may bring and maintain focus for the school, and this may influence performance.

On the other hand, parents who appreciate teachers would boost their motivation to give quality teaching and mentoring. When parents and teachers work together, the learners benefit a lot since support comes from the home and school. Discipline will also go up because teachers and parents monitor the child and minimal cases of truancy will be experienced. A study done by Sanders (2009), research findings have identified certain aspects of parents association that lowered truancy among students (Sanders and Sheldon, 2009; Sheldon, 2009). The PTA members were involved in monitoring pupil's whereabouts, thereby improving attendance and academic performance (Sanders and Sheldon, 2009).

The cooperation of PTA contributes to the academic performance of the school. The study results revealed an indication of an association of PTA cooperation and the academic performance of the school. Therefore, PTA cooperation in all aspects of the school is important to the performance of the school. This affirms the fact that PTA is an important organ as far as parental participation is concerned. The association primarily represents parent's decisions and is involved in formulating school policies and ensuring that such policies are implemented for quality education. The link between PTA cooperation and academic performance informs that due attention should be put into strengthening PTA associations for the betterment of the school.

Conclusions.

From the research findings, there existed a relationship between the cooperation (exhibited by parents through the PTA) and the academic achievement of schools and therefore concerted efforts need to be put in place in order to strengthen PTA representatives. Strengthening PTA will bring about improvement in academic achievement and therefore the cooperation of the PTA need to be enhanced. It comprises an important aspect that schools need to always look into with a view of making it stronger and stronger.

Recommendations

In relation to the study, there is a clear indication of the relationship that exists between the cooperation of school PTA and learner's achievement. The study findings indicated that PTA cooperation influenced school achievement in a great way, and therefore, there is need to strengthen PTA as an important organ charged with the many roles in the schools. PTA cooperation is contributing to pupils academic achievement (14.1%), and therefore the parent's body needs to be strengthened. In addition, a strong team of PTA members needs to be selected to provide leadership as far as management of schools is concerned.

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